

Study of the Biological Control Mechanism and its Pathogen on Sugarcane Crop in Nandurbar District.

Dr. M. H. Mali

Center for Post Graduate Studies and Research in Botany, C.H.C Arts, S.G.P Commerce and B.B.J.P Science College, Taloda, Dist Nandurbar, 425413

Abstract:

The present investigation encompasses aspects pertaining to disease control of various sugarcane crops by biological control mechanism. *Trichoderma viride*, *Baccillus subtilis* and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* are used against eight pathogenic fungi to understand comparative observations for inhibition zone in centimeter (cm) different pathogens affecting on sugarcane crops. Monoculture and duel culture experiment are taken to find out antimicrobial activity by useful microorganism. Result shows that in single culture experiment *T. viride* shows more inhibitory effects against *R. solani* followed by other pathogens at different levels of zone of inhibition.

Key words:- Biological control, pathogen, sugarcane, disease etc.

Introduction

Occurrence of various diseases on sugarcane crops, not only affects production or yields, but also affects its quality (Chupp and Sherf, 1960). Diseased sugarcanes get very less/ negligible prices in the market. Most of the diseases are very old in their occurrence although studied in great details in respect of pathogenesis, recurrence and control remedies (Walker, 1952) and the information on these aspect is readily available in the form of printed matter (Sokhi, 1994). Biological control against the pathogen is now a day's one of the most wonderful way of treatments in agriculture science.

Scientists all over the world have done extensive research to control the diseases of the crops by various other methods and come up with one of the most potential methods i.e. Biological Control. The late Harry Smith of the University of California, who defined it as "the suppression of insect population, coined the term biological control by the actions of their native or introduced enemies" Baker and Cook (1974) describe the bio control process as "the reduction of inoculum density of disease producing activities of pathogen or a parasite in cropping in its dormant state, by one or more organisms".

Biological control agents like *Trichoderma harzianum* are effective in managing diseases like root-rot, damping off and wilt caused by soil borne, plant pathogens like *Sclerotium rolfsii*, *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Pythium spp.*, *Phytophthora spp.*, *Fusarium spp.*, etc (Mukhopadhyay, 1987). Due to high cost and environmental concerns it is not advisable to protect the crops for entire period by conventional fungicides (Singh, 1978). Biological control, integration with fungicidal treatment is found to be more reliable approach to manage such soil born plant pathogens (Mukhopadhyay, 1987). There are reports on the compatibility of insecticide and fungicides with *Trichoderma spp.*, (Bhat and Srivastav, 2003, Patil and Khan 2017).

Antifungal activity of *Trichoderma viride*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* isolates are tested against *Fusarium moniliforme*, *Ustilago scitaminae*, *Colletotrichum falcatum*, *Bipolaris sacchari*, *Ceratocystis paradoxa*, *Helminthosporium sacchari*, *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Cephalosporium sacchari*, used separately in dual culture experiment.

Material and Methods

Trichoderma viride, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas* and cultures of different pathogens are obtained from the M.T.C.C. (Microbial type culture collection), Institute of microbial technology, Chandigarh.

The pathogen and *Trichoderma viride* allowed interacting in a petridish under optimum condition for both the pathogen and the bio control agent. Five ml of the aliquots with culture of each isolate were placed at a distance of 1.5 cm from the edge of petridis. A 5 mm disc of the test pathogens taken from the leading edge of the culture grown on medium was oppositely placed. Plates were then incubated and 28°C for 8 days until the leading edge of the test fungus reached the edge of the plate. Finally, beyond the zone of inhibition, the growth that developed was recorded (Varshney and Chaube, 1999 and Patil and Khan 2015). After 72 hrs. of inoculation inhibition zone was recorded in centimeter (cm). Sterile non-inoculated Nutrient Broth Yeast served as control.

Bacillus subtilis and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* strains were tested as per the modified method of Howell and Stripanovic (1983) for their ability to inhibit growth of various pathogenic fungi, on nutrient agar plates by streaking one to four single bacterial colonies around the edge of

a 90 mm diameter petriplate and incubating it at 28°C for 2 days. An agar plug inoculum of the fungi (5 mm square) was then transferred to the center of the plate individually from a source plate of pathogens, maintained on PDA for 2-7 days. After incubation for 2 additional days for *Fusarium moniliforme* and, *Rhizoctonia solani*, *Alternaria solani* and 5-7 additional days for and *Alternaria brassicicola* and *Alternaria solani* and *Colletotrichum fulcatum*. *Fusarium oxysporum* at 28 °C. Inhibition zones were readily observed in the case of bacterial strains having the biocontrol activity as the fungal growth around the streak was inhibited and inhibition zone was recorded in cm for all cases.

Result and Discussion

All three useful microorganisms i.e. *Trichoderma viride*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* (Image 1.0), showed inhibitory effects in dual culture on the growth of the pathogenic fungi namely *Fusarium moniliforme*, *Ustilago scitaminae*, *Colletotrichum falcatum*, *Bipolaris sacchari*, *Certocystis paradoxa*, *Helminthosporium sacchari*, *Rhizoctonia solani* and *Cephalosporium sacchari* (Image 2.0). The percentage inhibition of each pathogen as inhibited by *Trichoderma viride*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* in different modes of inhibition zone which was measured in cm for each case of study represented in Table 1.0 and their activity was plotted in graphs 4.

Image 1.0 a. *Trichoderma viride* b. *Bacillus subtilis* c. *Pseudomonas fluorescens*

Trichoderma viride in dual culture experiment (Image 3.0), which was tested against all eight pathogens stated above shows the best control of *Fusarium moniliforme* by 1.8 cm of zone of inhibition after inoculation. The second best result recorded against *Bipolaris sacchari* with 1.7 cm, followed by *Colletotrichum falcatum* with 1.4 cm, and *Certocystis paradoxa* by 1.3 cm of inhibition zone after inoculation of dual culture with minimum zone of inhibition is recorded

in *Rhizoctonia solani* with 0.86 cm indicating that *Trichoderma viride* are least efficient to control it as in Table 1.0 and representation in Graph 1.

Bipolaris sacchari

Cephalosporium sacchari

Ustilago scitaminae

Certocystis paradoxa

Fusarium moniliforme

Helminthosporium sacchari

Rhizoctonia solani

Colletotrichum falcatum

Image 2.0

Trichoderma viride with
Fusarium moniliforme

Trichoderma viride with
Rhizoctonia solani

Image 3.0

Pseudomonas fluorescent with
Fusarium moniliforme

Replicates	<i>Fusarium moniliforme</i>	<i>Ustilago citamiae</i>	<i>Colletotrichum falcatum</i>	<i>Bipolaris sacchari</i>	<i>Cercosyia paradoxa</i>	<i>Helminthosporium sacchari</i>	<i>Cephalosporium sacchari</i>	<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>
01	1.92	1.2	0.9	1.9	1.2	1.3	1.1	0.8
02	1.88	0.8	1.3	1.5	1.4	1.4	1.2	0.8
03	1.85	0.9	1.3	2.2	1.1	0.8	1.2	1.2
04	1.68	1.3	1.4	1.6	1.5	0.9	0.9	0.9
05	1.9	1.5	1.5	1.6	1.4	1.3	1	1
06	1.7	1.2	1.6	2.2	1.6	1.5	1.1	1.1
07	1.9	1	1.4	1.6	1.4	1.2	1.1	0.7
08	1.65	0.9	1.5	1.4	1.3	1	1.1	0.7
09	1.7	1.3	1.6	1.3	0.9	0.9	0.8	0.8
10	1.9	1.1	1.4	2.3	1.1	1.3	1.7	0.7
11	1.79	1.3	1.6	1.4	1.5	1.1	1.9	0.9
12	1.9	1.2	1.4	1.5	1.2	1.2	1.1	0.9
13	1.78	0.9	1.5	1.6	1.5	1.5	0.8	0.8
14	1.92	1.2	2.2	2.4	1.4	1.4	0.9	0.9
15	1.8	1.8	1.6	1.5	1.6	1.5	0.7	0.7
	1.8	1.1	1.4	1.7	1.3	1.2	1.1	0.86

Table 1.0 *Trichoderma viride* Dual Culture with following pathogens Zone of Inhibition in cm after 72 hrs. of treatment

Graph 1. *Trichoderma viride* Dual Culture with pathogen

For *Bacillus subtilis* result of dual culture showed inhibitory effects on the growth of the test fungi as follows: *Fusarium moniliforme* control best with 1.9 cm of zone of inhibition, followed by *Colletotrichum falcatum* and *Helminthosporium sacchari* by 1.4 cm of zone of inhibition and minimum zone of inhibition is recorded for *Rhizoctonia solani* 0.90 cm of zone of inhibition as in Table 2.0. and representations in Graph 2.

Replicates	<i>Fusarium moniliforme</i>	<i>Ustilago citamiae</i>	<i>Colletotrichum falcatum</i>	<i>Bipolaris sacchari</i>	<i>Cercosyria paradoxa</i>	<i>Helminthosporium sacchari</i>	<i>Cephalosporium sacchari</i>	<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>
01	1.2	1.4	1	1.2	1.1	1.5	1.2	0.8
02	1	0.8	1.3	1.1	1.5	1.4	0.9	1.1
03	1.9	0.7	1.4	2.2	1.2	1.2	1.2	0.9
04	1.68	1.3	1.3	1.6	1.4	1.9	1.1	1.2
05	1.9	1.5	1.5	2	1.5	1.5	0.9	1.1
06	2.7	1.2	1.6	1.4	1.2	1.7	1.2	0.8
07	1.9	1	1.5	1.6	1.3	1.3	0.7	0.7
08	1.65	1.6	1.1	1.4	0.9	1.2	0.8	0.7
09	2.7	0.9	1.6	1.2	1.1	1.5	1.1	0.8
10	1.9	1.1	1.2	2.1	1.6	1.8	0.9	1.2
11	1.79	1.3	1.6	1.4	1.4	1.7	1.2	1.1
12	1.9	1.2	1.4	1.5	1.5	1.2	1.1	0.9
13	2.58	0.9	1.5	1.6	1.41	1.5	0.8	1.2
14	1.7	2.1	1.9	2.1	1.2	1.4	1.1	0.7
15	2.8	1.8	1.1	1.5	1.4	1.4	0.8	0.7
	1.9	1.2	1.4	1.5	1.3	1.4	1.0	0.9

Table 2.0. *Bacillus subtilis* Dual Culture with following pathogens one of Inhibition in cm after 72 hrs. of treatment

Graph 2. *Bacillus subtilis* Dual Culture with pathogen

Pseudomonas fluorescens showed best inhibition of growth against *Fusarium moniliforme* by 1.7 cm same result is recorded for *Colletotrichum falcatum*, were *Bipolaris sacchari* shows 1.6 cm inhibition zone after 72 hrs. of treatment, followed by *Helminthosporium sacchari* with 1.5 cm and *Certocystis paradoxa* by 1.3 cm. Minimum zone of inhibition is recorded in *Rhizoctonia solani* with 1.02 cm of zone of inhibition as in Table 3.0 and representations in Graph 3.

Replicates	<i>Fusarium moniliforme</i>	<i>Ustilago scitaminae</i>	<i>Colletotrichum falcatum</i>	<i>Bipolaris sacchari</i>	<i>Certocystis paradoxa</i>	<i>Helminthosporium sacchari</i>	<i>Cephalosporium sacchari</i>	<i>Rhizoctonia solani</i>
01	1.6	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.4	1.6	1.3	0.8
02	1.5	0.8	1.9	1.2	1.6	2	1.2	1.1
03	2.1	1	1.9	2.2	1.2	1.7	1.3	1.1
04	2	1.3	2.4	1.2	1.5	1.9	1.2	1.2
05	0.8	1.2	2.2	2	1.5	1.5	1.2	1
06	1.9	1.2	1.8	1.4	1.5	1.7	1.3	1.1
07	2.1	1.6	1.9	1.8	1.3	1.2	1.2	1.2

08	2	1.6	2.1	1.4	1.2	1.2	0.9	0.9
09	2.2	1.2	2	1.5	1.6	1.3	1.1	1.1
10	1.8	1.1	1.2	2.1	1.6	1.8	1.3	1.2
11	1.2	1.5	1.5	1.2	1.4	1.7	0.9	0.9
12	1.33	1.2	1.4	1.5	1.2	1.4	1.4	0.8
13	1.5	1.2	1.4	1.9	1.41	1.5	1.4	0.9
14	2	1.9	1.8	2.1	1.2	1.9	1.1	1.1
15	2.1	1.7	1.2	2.1	1.2	1.4	1.3	0.9
	1.7	1.3	1.7	1.6	1.3	1.5	1.2	1.02

Table 3.0. *Pseudomonas fluorescens* Dual Culture with following pathogens Zone of Inhibition in cm after 72 hrs. of treatment

Graph 3. *Pseudomonas fluorescens* Dual Culture with pathogen

Cumulative results were analyzed from mean value of each beneficial microorganism versus all eight pathogenic fungi to understand comparative observations for inhibition zone in center meters (Table 4.0.). It is observed that, highest result for growth inhibition is recorded against *Fusarium moniliforme* followed by *Bipolaris sacchari*, *Colletotrichum falcatum* and *Helminthes sporiumsacchari* were recorded as least effective for *Rhizoctonia solani* among all pathogenic fungi (Graph 4.).

Beneficial organisms in dual culture	<i>Fusariummoniliforme</i>	<i>Ustilagos citaminae</i>	<i>Colletotrichum falcatum</i>	<i>Bipolaris sacchari</i>	<i>Certocystis paradoxa</i>	<i>Helminthosoriussacchari</i>	<i>Cephalsporiumsacchari</i>	<i>Rhizoctoniasolani</i>
<i>Trichoderma viride</i>	1.8	1.1	1.4	1.7	1.3	1.2	1.1	0.86
<i>Baccillus subtilis</i>	1.9	1.2	1.4	1.5	1.3	1.4	1.0	0.9
<i>Pseudomonas fluorescens</i>	1.7	1.3	1.7	1.6	1.3	1.5	1.2	1.02

Table 4.0. Pathogens in Dual Culture Experiments cumulative inhibition cm

Graph 4.Cumulative Graphical representations of all Dual Culture with pathogen

Conclusion

T. viride showed more inhibitory effects against *R. solani*. It reduced the growth of parasite at significant level, while *B. subtilis* also indicated more inhibitory results against it followed by *P. fluorescens*. Similar observations are recorded by Chaurasia (1984) in dual culture when colony of *A. niger* and *R. solani* came in close proximity. Hyphae of *A. niger* run parallel and ultimately coiled around the hyphae of *R. solani* in vitro. Later on the hyphae developed

infection peg, which penetrated the host hyphae. Earlier Chaurasia (1984), showed that the growth of the *Asparagus* plants was prompted only by *T. viride* (85/1) spore mixed with sand, it's cultures on beet pulp and *T. harzianum* cultures on wheat kernels. *T. viride* alone increased plant dry weight considerably compared to untreated control (Entz, 2001).

References

1. Baker, K.F. and Cook, R.J. (1974): "Biological control of plant pathogens" W.H. Freeman and co., San Francisco.
2. Bhat M.N. and Srivastav, L. (2003): Evaluation of some fungicides and neem formulation against six soil-borne pathogens and three *Trichoderma spp. in vitro*. *Pl. Dis. Res.* 18: 56-59.
3. Chaurasia, SNP. (1984): Ph.D Thesis. Banara Hindu University.
4. Chupp, C. and Sherf, A.F. (1960): Sugarcane diseases and their control, 690 P. Ronald Press.
5. Entz M.H., Guilford R, and Gulden R (2001): Productivity of organic crop production in the eastern region of the Northern Great Plains: A survey of 14 farms. *Can J Plant Sci* 81:351-354.
6. Howell, C. R., Stipanovic, R. D. (1983): Gliovirin, a new antibiotic from *Gliocladiumvirens*, and its role in the biological control of *Pythiummultimum*. *Can. J. Microbiol.* 29: 321-324.
7. M. B. Patil and P. A. Khan (2017). Ethnobotanical, phytochemical and Fourier Transform Infrared Spectrophotometer (FTIR) studies of *Catunaregam spinosa* (Thunb.) Tirven. *Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. Vol. 10 Issue 2 PP 950-955 (UGC Approved Journal Sr. No 21822.)
8. Mukhopadhyay, A.N. (1987) : Biological control of soil borne plant pathogens by *Trichoderma spp.* *Indian J. Mycol. Pl. pathol.* 17: 1-10.
9. Patil M. B. and Khan P. A. (2015). Ethnomedicinal Studies of *Acalypha Indica* L. (Euphorbiaceae). *Review of Research Journal*, V (4) 7 PP-1-6.
10. Singh, K. (1978): Pelletting of sugar beet for control of seeding mortality due to *Pythium*. *Indian J. Sugarcane Tech.* 1: 3-67.
11. Sokhi, S.S. (1994): Integrated approaches in management of vegetable diseases in India. *Indian Phytopath.* 47(4): 371-375

12. Varshney and Chaube**(1999)**: Indian j. plant pathology. 17 (1&2) 59-61.
13. Walker. J.C. **(1952)**: Diseases of Vegetable Crops. McGrawHill.Co.Inc. N.Y. pp. 529.